

No entry: Encounters with Social and Cultural Capital when seeking educational settings to conduct research.

Melissa Lynch

Melissa.lynch69@mail.dcu.ie

Abstract

This article outlines a novice researcher's experience while seeking access to sample populations in schools for data collection. The overall research project aims to investigate how social and cultural capital impacts student progression to higher and further education and training from DEIS Post Primary schools. This article presents the ongoing difficulties in gaining entry into these settings and how social and cultural capital can influence the success of researchers in gaining access. Current university ethical requirements require permissions from 'gatekeepers' in key positions in potential settings to access participants with the need for GDPR and ethical adherence leading to stricter protocols for accessing sample populations for qualitative research. Increasingly, research in education must be balanced with the increasing workload and societal demands on teachers and management across all education and training domains. This article explores the influence of social and cultural capital on researchers and the practice of ethical data collection methodologies with a focus on the barriers novice researchers face when seeking access and entry into educational settings. However, it is important to note that this challenge extends beyond the realm of education and applies to all disciplines conducting research involving human participants.

Keywords:

Access, Cultural Capital, Social Capital, Researcher challenges, Post-Primary, Gatekeepers

Three Key Highlights:

- **Access:** Social and cultural capital can determine researchers' ability to gain entry into educational settings impacting their access to sample populations.
- **Trust and Engagement:** Researchers with higher social and cultural capital may find establishing trust and rapport with gatekeepers and participants easier leading to more meaningful and insightful data.
- **Methodological Considerations:** Cultural capital influences researchers' understanding and use of appropriate research methodologies and academic discourse within educational settings.

Introduction

The overarching goal of any research study is to advance existing knowledge (Garg, 2016) or to acquire new information and understanding by using specific settings and research methods (Clarke & Visser, 2019). It is an ongoing search to understand the complexities of the world around us, led by specific situations and rigorous inquiry techniques. However, for ambitious novice researchers, the path can be blocked with distinct and unusually challenging obstacles from the very beginning, including getting their foot in the door, gaining access to their desired research settings and sample populations, navigating their way through complex protocols, hierarchies, and the scepticism of overloaded gatekeepers. For many novice researchers, limited social and cultural capital poses significant challenges when seeking access to research settings and sample populations (Oates & Riaz, 2016); however, with established networks and experience, they may be able to build connections, gain trust with gatekeepers, and navigate those complex protocols.

The Novice Researcher: The author's current research is an exploratory case study of the Impact of Social and Cultural Capital on Low Socioeconomic Status (LSES) Students Progression from Delivering Equality of Opportunity in Schools (DEIS) Schools in Ireland.

The overall aim of this research study is to explore the impact that social and cultural capital plays in students' perceptions and aspirations from LSES when participating in education and considering the transition to Higher Education/Further Education and Training (HE/FET). Research questions include does social capital influence young peoples' (YP) perceptions?, does cultural capital affect YP's understanding of educational engagement and progression?, and does the support and guidance available to YP affect their educational choices? There appears to be very little qualitative research in the empirical literature that explores different aspects of participation and access to HE/FET from the perspectives of students, their families (Scanlon *et al.*, 2019) and the social and cultural barriers that impact their education participation and progression from LSES in Ireland. Some of these barriers include but are not limited to social, cultural, and educational barriers (Hannon et al., 2017). The author's research will explore whether societal understanding of human culture, analysis, and application is insufficient to comprehend whether societal understanding of the influence of social and cultural capital on YP's aspirations for progression from DEIS school is inhibiting their decision-making processes. The author encountered various impediments while attempting to secure samples for data collection in educational settings. The author who had completed a comprehensive research design and obtained ethical approval hypothesised that the lack of responses from setting may be due to her lack of social and cultural capital. As a novice researcher lacking established networks and prior knowledge in the field of education makes it difficult to acquire access to research settings and sample populations. The author received eight non-responses and avoidance from gatekeepers upon follow up calls to the schools emphasising their scepticism and reluctance, this realisation prompted the author to recognise the relevance of social and cultural capital in research and the need to overcome access challenges while developing networks and connections in future research.

As novice researchers conducting research the importance of informal and tacit knowledge, familiarity with educational networks and recognition as an affiliated researcher can provide access to educational opportunities, information, and support, influencing academic achievement and social mobility (Bourdieu, 1973). Novice researchers, especially those from diverse backgrounds or with minimal experience in the educational system, may need to help comprehend cultural nuances and gain the trust of gatekeepers to successfully undertake their proposed and approved research samples with their desired participants.

This article explores how gaining access to educational settings for research purposes is a challenging task (Kondowe and Booyens, 2014) especially for novice researchers and those who do not yet possess social and cultural capital within their field or chosen research area. According to Oats and Riaz (2016, p. 67), the "lack of social and cultural capital can be barriers to negotiating entry and participating in the field of educational research". Bourdieu's (1986, pp. 241-258) conceptualisation of cultural capital, encompassing knowledge and competencies, contributes to our understanding of how these attributes shape researchers' ability to navigate research environments and establish rapport with participants; he also argues that social capital in education refers to the resources and advantages that individuals gain through their social networks and relationships. This article outlines the author's reflections during the commencement of a long-term research project. It specifically outlines the difficulties encountered by the author in seeking and gaining access to educational settings for data collection. The article highlights the persistent challenges that impact and can confront novice researchers as they navigate the complicated landscape of educational research, while also exploring the influence of social and cultural capital on accessing and engaging with identified sample settings. Through a reflective approach, these difficulties will be interpreted within the scope of traditional social and cultural capital frameworks, as exemplified by Bourdieu (1986, pp. 46-58) and Patton (2014, pp. 381-386).

Methods/Conceptual Framework

This article presents the significance of social and cultural capital in the design of a research project methodology when seeking sample populations for data collection. It draws attention to the challenges experienced by the author as a novice postgraduate researcher attempting to access DEIS post-primary schools for their qualitative research project. The article emphasises how the absence of social and cultural capital can notably impact both the research process and the researcher. These insights emerged through analysis of the author's reflective diary and discussions with their supervisors.

Methods: According to Johnson (2009, pp. 23-50) Reflection diaries serve to capture the researcher's subjective experiences, self-awareness, and personal growth throughout the research journey. Researchers often use reflection diaries to analyse their own perspectives, biases, and preconceptions that may influence the research process and outcomes (Vinjamuri, *et al.*, 2017). By regularly maintaining a reflection diary, researchers can develop a deeper understanding of their own role in the research process, enabling them to critically evaluate their methods, decisions, and interpretations. This self-reflection can contribute to the overall rigor and reflexivity of the research study (Jamieson *et al.*, 2023). Through the author's active engagement in discussions with supervisors, this process served as a reflective method in their research process. These exchanges provided the author with a platform to critically assess their hypothesis regarding the significance of social and cultural capital as a novice researcher when seeking access to sample populations. Discussions and subsequent reflection facilitated the author by collaborating with an experienced supervisor, the author gained deeper insights into potential biases, ultimately enhancing the quality and credibility of their research findings.

The method in this study was grounded in a reflexive examination of the author's personal experiences in seeking sample populations and the author's ability to critically reflect on one's

practice and engage in continuous learning and development (Schon, 1983). Reflection is an active process of self-observation to gain a deeper understanding of experiences. It involves stepping back or engaging in separate reflection. Through an examination of the author's reflection diary and discussions with supervisors, the author uncovered valuable insights derived from their personal experiences, encompassing both internal and external events before, during, or after they transpired (Amulya, 2004). Reflexivity entails researchers deliberately and consciously recognising, analysing, and divulging their identities within the context of their research, intending to comprehend their role in and influence the research process (Cohen *et al.*, 2018). Through introspection and critical self-reflection, the author raised awareness of how their own social and cultural capital and potential biases influenced the selection of sample populations and access to desired settings. As Hertz (1997, p.40) put it, "To be reflexive is to have an ongoing conversation about the experience while simultaneously living in the moment", and this reflexive approach acknowledges that the author's characteristics, experiences, beliefs, values, knowledge, and perspectives can shape the sampling process (Cohen *et al.*, 2018, p. 302-303). In reflective practice, by systematically reflecting on experiences, the author sought to explore the impact of social and cultural capital to succeed in engaging with desired settings and enhance the rigour and validity of the study while ensuring that sample settings are selected in an informed and unbiased manner (Preissle, 2006). This reflexive examination provides a unique lens to approach the sampling process, enrich the overall research design, and contribute a more nuanced understanding of the phenomena under investigation (Finlay, 2002).

Conceptual Framework: The conceptual framework for this study draws mainly on the works of Bourdieu (1986) and Patton (2014). As outlined in "The Forms of Capital" (1986, pp. 46-58), Bourdieu's concept of cultural capital highlights the role of knowledge, competencies, and social networks in shaping researchers' access to and engagement with educational settings.

His work contributes to the authors understanding of the influence of social and cultural capital on researchers' ability to navigate research environments and establish rapport with participants, while Patton's contributions to qualitative research, notably the publication of "Qualitative Research and Evaluation Methods" (2014, pp. 381-386) emphasise the significance of reflexive practices and critical self-reflection in enhancing the rigour and validity of qualitative studies. The proposed framework incorporates Patton's insights to ensure a thoughtful and self-aware approach to participant selection by examining the author's subjectivity and potential biases. Furthermore, the conceptual framework considers the author's perspectives on their experiences as a novice postgraduate researcher. These experiences involve efforts to secure access to settings for qualitative research in DEIS post-primary schools in Dublin. The framework integrates Finlay's (2002) theory of the process and practice of reflexivity in qualitative research, along with insights from Oates and Riaz's (2016) exploration of methodological challenges related to accessing educational settings for research.

By integrating these theoretical perspectives, the conceptual framework aims to provide a comprehensive perception of the influences of social and cultural capital, reflection, reflexivity, and qualitative research principles on novice researchers' access to educational settings for research purposes and emphasises the need to address these factors ethically and rigorously. This framework will guide the author in navigating the complexities of gaining access to settings, contributing to a more nuanced understanding of the research topic.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are of the utmost importance when establishing research methodologies and ensuring the ethical and sensitive treatment of participants, as well as the broader implications of the research (Cohen et al., 2018, pp. 111-141). Ethical issues seeking

participation from vulnerable groups surrounding social and cultural capital regarding access to settings are multifaceted and require careful research (Walker & Read, 2013). The author did not require ethical approval for this article as it is based on reflection and dialogue without data from sample participants. However, the author first became aware of potential obstacles to data collection with identified samples when seeking ethical approval. The author encountered the first obstacle when seeking ethical approval to begin conducting educational research and data sampling. Although adhering to all ethical guidelines for submission for approval, the author experienced numerous delays due to response times and communication with the Data Protection Unit (DPU) and the Research Ethics Committee (REC) resulting in a total delay of four months. Despite eventually obtaining ethical approval and adhering to the institution's standards, the author subsequently encountered further unforeseen obstacles and challenges in gaining access to the research settings and recruiting participants.

Accessing educational research settings is significantly influenced by gatekeepers, with highlighting the ethical challenge faced was the potential for gatekeepers to exercise undue influence or favouritism in granting access to settings or populations based on their own social and cultural capital. Recently, the influx of research requests, exacerbated by the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic (Patel et al., 2020 pp. 445-455), has overwhelmed gatekeepers in education and gatekeepers who hold positions of authority or influence within these settings. As a result of the high volume of research inquiries, gatekeepers may become more selective or cautious in granting access, highlighting the importance of establishing solid relationships, demonstrating credibility, and effectively communicating the value of the proposed research to overcome these barriers and that ethical approval is not enough as a stand-alone to gain entry. These additional challenges for ethical research and data collection raises the importance of the supervisors' roles and their support.

Supervisors are responsible for guiding and supporting researchers (Cardilini et al, 2022), particularly novice researchers, in navigating the ethical challenges associated with social and cultural capital. They should promote awareness of power dynamics, potential biases, and ethical considerations regarding accessing settings. They can encourage open discussions about the ethical implications of social and cultural capital in research and guide novice researchers on how to address these issues responsibly. Supervisors can offer insights into approaching gatekeepers, establishing trust, and navigating complex protocols, respectfully and ethically (Löfström & Pyhältö, 2014, pp.195-214). Supervisors should also encourage reflexivity by facilitating critical self-reflection on their own social and cultural biases and the potential impact of their positionality on the research process. This support can help researchers to recognise and address ethical issues during the access phase (Muthanna & Alduais, 2021, pp 95 -113).

Discussion and Analysis

This article explores how the impact of social and cultural capital influences the experience of novice researchers when seeking to gain access to sample populations in educational settings. Through the utilisation of reflection diaries and discussions with supervisors, several findings were revealed. Firstly, the author experienced challenges gaining entry to desired research settings and sample populations which through the authors' reflections highlighted the significant impact of social and cultural capital on researchers' ability to gain entry, access participants and data sources (Bourdieu, 1986). Novice researchers, who lack established networks and prior knowledge in the field, face challenges in building connections, gaining trust with gatekeepers, and navigating complex protocols. Trust and engagement also emerge as crucial factors influenced by social and cultural capital. Researchers with higher social and cultural capital find it easier to establish trust and rapport with gatekeepers and participants

which may generate more meaningful and insightful data, emphasising the role of networks and connections in gaining access to educational opportunities, information, and support, which can positively influence researchers' academic achievement and social mobility (Bourdieu, 1973, pp. 53 - 80).

In terms of methodological considerations related to social and cultural capital, novice researchers, especially those from diverse backgrounds or with minimal experience in the educational system, may struggle to comprehend cultural nuances and gain gatekeepers' trust. It could be argued that cultural capital influences understanding and employing appropriate research methodologies and academic discourse within educational settings (Bourdieu, 1986).

The article further highlights the potential for gatekeepers to exercise undue influence or favouritism based on their social and cultural capital, compromising the ethical integrity of the research. Moreover, in accessing the settings and role of supervisors was also addressed, noting how supervisors play a crucial role in guiding researchers through ethical challenges, promoting reflexivity, and advocating for equitable access.

In conclusion this discussion and analysis underscores the importance of considering the influence of social and cultural capital when addressing barriers to accessing educational settings for research purposes and emphasises the need for ethical conduct, reflexivity, and supportive supervision to overcome these challenges.

Limitations

While this article offers insights into the challenges faced by novice researchers when accessing educational settings for research purposes, it is imperative to acknowledge its inherent limitations. The findings stem from the author's specific experiences as a novice postgraduate researcher conducting qualitative research in DEIS post-primary schools in Ireland, thus limiting their generalisability. Furthermore, the study primarily focuses on the aspect of access

to educational settings leaving unexplored other potential influential factors or research disciplines, indicating avenues for further investigation.

Finally, this article does not examine the potential intersectionality of social and cultural capital with other areas, such as race, gender, and ethnicity, which may contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the challenges and difficulties faced by novice researchers in all fields.

Conclusion

This article concludes by highlighting the challenges novice researchers experience in accessing educational settings for research purposes, in addition to the crucial role of social and cultural capital in this process. The discussion and analysis suggest that social and cultural capital can impact researchers' access to participants and data sources by affecting their ability to enter educational settings. Social and cultural capital influences trust and engagement, with higher levels of capital facilitating the establishment of trust and rapport with gatekeepers and participants.

Based on the works of Bourdieu (1986) and Patton (2014) as a conceptual framework, their theories provide an insight into the influences of social and cultural capital, reflexivity, and qualitative research principles on access to educational settings. Ethical considerations regarding access are discussed, with the potential for gatekeepers to exert undue influence and the significance of supportive supervision noted.

Acknowledging the study's limitations is essential, based primarily on the author's personal experiences in a particular context. The findings may not apply to all novice researchers, and further research is required to investigate the intersection of social and cultural capital with other factors and to increase the understanding of this field. Overall, this article emphasises the need to consider social and cultural capital when addressing barriers to accessing educational

settings for research and to promote ethical conduct, reflexivity, and supportive supervision to overcome obstacles and enhance the rigour of educational research.

References

- Amulya, J. (2004). What is reflective practice. Centre for Reflective Community Practice, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, MA. [Online] Available at: <https://www.itslifejambutnotasweknowit.org.uk/files/whatisreflectivepractice.pdf>. (Accessed 02nd July 2023).
- Bourdieu, P. (1973). The three forms of theoretical knowledge. *Social Science Information*, 12(1), pp.53-80.
- Bourdieu, P. (1986). The forms of capital. In J. G. Richardson (Ed.), *Handbook of theory and research for the sociology of education* (pp. 241-258). Greenwood Press.
- Cardilini, A.P., Risely, A. and Richardson, M.F., (2022). Supervising the PhD: identifying common mismatches in expectations between candidate and supervisor to improve research training outcomes. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 41(3), pp.613-627.
- Clarke, E. and Visser, J., (2019). ‘Pragmatic research methodology in education: possibilities and pitfalls. *International Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 42(5), pp.455-469.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2018). *Research methods in education*. London: Routledge.
- Evans, L., (2002). *Reflective practice in educational research*. A&C Black.
- Finlay, L., (2002). “Outing” the researcher: The provenance, process, and practice of reflexivity. *Qualitative health research*, 12(4), pp.531-545.
- Garg, R., (2016). ‘Methodology for research I.’ *Indian journal of anaesthesia*, 60(9), p.640.
- Hannon, C., Faas, D. and O'Sullivan, K., (2017). Widening the educational capabilities of socio-economically disadvantaged students through a model of social and cultural capital development. *British Educational Research Journal*, 43(6), pp.1225-1245.
- Hertz, R. (1997). *Reflexivity and voice*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Jamieson, M.K., Govaart, G.H. and Pownall, M., (2023). Reflexivity in quantitative research: A rationale and beginner's guide. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, p.e12735.
- Johnson, N., (2009). The role of self and emotion within qualitative sensitive research: A reflective account. *Enquire*, 2(4), pp.23-50.
- Kondowe, C. and Booyens, M. (2014). A student’s experience of gaining access for qualitative research, *Social Work/Maatskaplike Werk*, 50(1). doi: 10.15270/50-1-21.
- Löfström, E. and Pyhältö, K., (2014). Ethical issues in doctoral supervision: The perspectives of PhD students in the natural and behavioural sciences. *Ethics & Behavior*, 24(3), pp.195-214.
- Muthanna, A. and Alduais, A., (2021). A thematic review on research integrity and research supervision: Relationships, Crises and Critical Messages. *Journal of Academic Ethics*, 19, pp.95-113.
- Oates, C., and Riaz, N. N. (2016). Accessing the field: methodological difficulties of research in schools. *Education in the North*, 23(2), pp.53-74.
- Patel, S.S., Webster, R.K., Greenberg, N., Weston, D., and Brooks, S.K., (2020). ‘Research fatigue in COVID-19 pandemic and post-disaster research: causes, consequences, and

recommendations. *Disaster Prevention and Management: An International Journal*, 29(4), pp.445-455. Patton, M. (2015) *Qualitative Research and Evaluation Methods*. SAGE Publications.

Patton, M.Q., (2014). *Qualitative research & evaluation methods: Integrating theory and practice*. Sage publications.

Preissle, J., (2006). Envisioning qualitative inquiry: A view across four decades. *International journal of qualitative studies in education*, 19(6), pp.685-695.

Scanlon, M., Jenkinson, H., Leahy, P., Powell, F. and Byrne, O., (2019). 'How are we going to do it?' An exploration of the barriers to access to higher education amongst young people from disadvantaged communities. *Irish Educational Studies*, 38(3), pp.343-357.

Schon, D.A. (1983). *The reflective practitioner: How professionals think in action*. New York: Basic Books.

Walker, S. and Read, S., (2011). 'Accessing vulnerable research populations: an experience with gatekeepers of ethical approval.' *International journal of palliative nursing*, 17(1), pp.14-18.

Vinjamuri, M., Warde, B. and Kolb, P., (2017). The reflective diary: An experiential tool for enhancing social work students' research learning. *Social Work Education*, 36(8), pp.933-945.